

The Brightest Representation Of Our National Values Are Traditions

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Abstract: This article talks about education, the role of national values in educating the younger generation to be physically healthy and spiritually mature, spiritual heritage, national traditions.

INTRODUCTION

Education and upbringing have always been one of the most pressing issues. Regarding the state policy aimed at educating the younger generation, our President Shavkat Mirziyoyev says: “We will mobilize all the forces and capabilities of our state and society so that our young people can develop and be happy, becoming independent thinkers, possessing high intellectual and spiritual potential, and who are not inferior to their peers in any field on a global scale.”

It is especially important to ensure the continuity of education and upbringing in the general education system. In preparing the younger generation to be physically healthy and spiritually mature, the scientific and practical study of issues such as studying the works of classical writers, highlighting the educational and educational significance of their works, and forming moral qualities in young students is gaining relevance today. Today, the task of the school is not only to prepare educated students, but also to form spiritually and morally perfect individuals. In fulfilling such a socially significant national task, it is an important didactic necessity to create an opportunity for students to get acquainted with the immortal examples of classical literature. Among the subjects taught in secondary schools, the subject of literature occupies a leading position in the formation of noble spiritual qualities in students. Because literature has unparalleled opportunities to create a state of mind, understanding, imagination, mood, hopes, inclinations and interests that make up the spiritual image of a person. It is a boundless field for determining the spiritual world of students. The study of classical works from a pedagogical point of view is so relevant that the guidelines for transforming this spiritual process into a process of education and upbringing in the literal sense become socially significant and socially necessary. Therefore, in our country,

attention is being paid to classical literature, which is our spiritual heritage, and to reading books at the government level. At the national level, the Presidential decrees, orders and other regulatory legal acts serve as the primary methodological basis in this regard.

The fourth direction of the “Strategy of Actions for the Further Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan” adopted by the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-4947 dated February 7, 2017, called “Development of the social sphere”, such as “Educating physically healthy, spiritually and intellectually developed, free-thinking, loyal to the Motherland, with a firm life outlook, increasing their social activity in the process of deepening democratic reforms and developing civil society”, is directly related to book reading and classical fiction. It is a well-known fact that such high spiritual qualities are cultivated in young people in the process of reading and studying, among other pedagogical activities, a reading culture, and excellent works of national and world literature.

As a logical continuation of this, the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-60 dated January 28, 2022 “On the new Development Strategy of Uzbekistan for 2022-2026” can be said to have been an important event in the social and spiritual life of our country. This decree gave impetus to a re-perception of the role and importance of fiction in the formation of human morals, the rise of spirituality and the expansion of worldview in society, including among young people, and its practical application in the life of society. The fifth priority area of the decree, entitled “ensuring spiritual development and bringing the sector to a new level”, includes the following: transforming a healthy worldview and creativity into a nationwide movement in society by widely promoting the idea of “From a Strategy of Actions to a Strategy of Development” based on the

principles of goodness and humanity; implementing the concept of “New Uzbekistan - an Enlightened Society”, organizing legal and educational activities to form a legal culture among the population in harmony with the rich history, scientific and cultural heritage of our people, and teaching national and religious values; providing state support for the preservation, wide popularization and development of the national values and spiritual heritage of the Uzbek people; ensuring the continuity of spiritual education in the family, educational organizations and neighborhoods; developing scientifically based indicators for assessing spiritual education; and equipping schools with truly spiritual and enlightened, cultural Special attention is paid to the use of interactive methods of education, in-depth study and wide dissemination of the rich scientific heritage of our great ancestors.

Bugungi kunda mamlakatimizning barcha soha va tarmoqlarida ulkan o'zgarishlar amalga oshirilmoqda. Bu borada jamiyat hayotida ezgu qadriyat va an'analarni chuqur qaror toptirishga, xususan, xalqimiz, ayniqsa, yosh avlodning ma'naviy-intellektual salohiyati, ong-u tafakkuri va dunyoqarashini yuksaltirish, ularning qalbida ona Vatanimiz hamda xalqimizga muhabbat va sadoqat tuyg'usini kuchaytirish, barkamol shaxsni tarbiyalashda beqiyos ahamiyatga ega bo'lgan kitobxonlik madaniyatini oshirishga alohida e'tibor qaratilmoqda.

The Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PQ-3721 dated May 15, 2018 “On the organization of reading competitions among young people in order to widely study and promote the creative heritage of our great scientists, writers and thinkers” was a bold step in creating a practical mechanism for the implementation of these documents. These regulatory documents set a cross-cutting task for methodologists and pedagogical scientists, educators of preschool educational institutions to study the need to instill the national values into their consciousness, psyche, and spiritual world, as well as to educate the younger generation in the spirit of reading from an early age, and to create a scientific and methodological basis for this task. In this regard, it is natural that manifestations of national values - customs, family culture, medical culture, cultural heritage, culture of behavior and clothing will be the objects of these studies.

National customs are a form of behavior, rules of conduct and skills adopted by the majority, which are embedded in the way of life of a nation, serve its formation and development, are constantly repeated, are reflected in its social and cultural

life. National customs have their own unique historical characteristics in our people and are manifested in traditional and modern forms. National customs are formed within the framework of a particular person and nation. For example, among Uzbeks, younger people greet older people, get up early and sweep the yard, show special respect to guests, and check on the health of the sick and suffering, those in need of help, and the elderly on the eve of the holiday. During the authoritarian regime, many of our traditions were trampled on as relics of the past, which negatively affected the education of young people, the preservation of national identity, and thereby the spiritual development of the Uzbek nation. National traditions are formed and improved under the influence of the history, traditions, folk oral literature, art and literature, lifestyle and other factors of the nation and people.

Traditions are the brightest manifestation of our national values, and are considered one of the most important signs of the nation, therefore, it is necessary to instill these values in the minds of children from an early age - from kindergarten. Because as traditions are forgotten, national identity also begins to be lost: “The older generation taught young people to work, to keep their homes, streets, alleys and squares clean. This was a tradition for us. Now some people are letting their yard be cleaned by a laborer, not by their children. In apartment buildings, neighbors do not recognize their neighbors. In this case, from whom will children learn work, decency, spirituality, and kindness? The biggest threat to our spirituality is the growing indifference and carelessness of most of our people. ” These words of our President Sh. Mirziyoyev were aimed at a deeper understanding and feeling of the importance of traditions, which are considered leading national values. It is not for nothing that the head of the country emphasizes this value - it is an important factor in preserving national identity (mentality). This meaning is also expressed in the definitions of national identity given by philosophers: “The aspiration to understand that each nation (people) is a real subject, a representative of certain material and spiritual wealth, a single language, customs, traditions, values, and belonging to the state, a common set of interests and needs is called national identity.”

When it comes to national values, special attention is paid to national holidays, because it is in the preschool educational organization that the role, influence, and opportunities of holidays in raising children are incomparable. The love of holidays inherent in human nature, their anticipation, and celebration in a high mood are more clearly manifested in children. Today, in many countries, in particular, in our country, this factor is of particular importance. “Social-

emotional learning (SEL) is the process of developing self-awareness, self-regulation, and interpersonal relationships that are essential for success in school, work, and life.”

Holidays, from the thousand-year-old Navruz to Islamic holidays and Independence Day celebrations, are a great pedagogical tool for the formation of national consciousness, national pride, and national character, opening up great opportunities for every educator in the process of celebrating them with the participation of the whole nation. For example, Independence Day, as a value that, in the words of our President, “restored our human dignity, pride and honor, our religion and faith, and our national statehood,” instills in children from an early age a sense of identity and patriotism. Along with nationality, Navruz is considered a great opportunity to educate the younger generation in the spirit of spiritual closeness, internationalism, mutual respect, and harmony with our fraternal nations, as well as the peoples of the East. Therefore, in 2010, the UN declared March 21 as the International Navruz Day. In 2016, the Navruz holiday was included in the UNESCO Intangible Cultural Heritage List.

In the same sense, the days of Ramadan and Kurban are widely celebrated in our country, the reason for which is explained by the head of the country as follows: “... our noble people, living with great dreams of achieving the happiness of two worlds, will certainly achieve great achievements by effectively using these opportunities in the spiritual *upbringing of the growing young generation.*”

In conclusion, it can be said that every nation and people have their own national values. It is the duty of every person to educate the younger generation on the basis of national values. Respect for the older generation should be an example for the younger generation.

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